

A Hands-On Curriculum for Training in HPC Cluster Deployment and Management

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Abstract—This paper presents the design, methodology, and outcomes of the High-Performance Computing Technologies (HPCT) course, a hands-on training program focused on the system-side of HPC cluster deployment and administration. Delivered as part of the Master in High Performance Computing (MHPC) program, the course introduces students to key concepts in cluster configuration, including networking, software stack provisioning, job scheduling, and monitoring. Initially taught in person, the course was transitioned to an online format during the COVID-19 pandemic. This shift led to the development of openly available instructional material and a flipped-classroom approach that continues to support both in-person and hybrid delivery. All course materials are publicly available at www.hpc.temple.edu/mhpc/hpc-technology/index.html. By documenting the structure, infrastructure, and evolution of HPCT, this paper offers a model for accessible HPC system training that supports workforce development in computational science.

Index Terms—High-Performance Computing Education, HPC Cluster deployment and configuration, System Administration, Online Teaching

I. INTRODUCTION

High-performance computing (HPC) plays a critical role in advancing scientific discovery across a wide range of fields. The increasing complexity of computational tools and the scale of HPC systems have created a strong demand for educational programs that provide students with a solid foundation in HPC [1] [2].

While there is strong coverage in user-facing HPC training events and programs, addressing a wide variety of topics from foundational skills, such as accessing and using an HPC cluster, to more advanced topics, such as parallel programming, source code optimization, and HPC algorithm implementation, there remains a gap in educational offerings for system-facing professionals. Specifically, there is a need for training focused on individuals capable of building, configuring, and operating HPC clusters, as well as working with complex

software stacks, diverse hardware environments, and evolving toolchains.

One initiative that addresses this training need is the High-Performance Computing Technologies (HPCT) course, part of the Master in HPC (MHPC) program [3], organized by the International School for Advanced Studies (SISSA) and the International Center for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) in Italy. The MHPC is a one-year graduate program structured in three parts. The first part, *Introduction to HPC and Programming*, provides foundational knowledge in parallel programming and software engineering. The second part, *HPC Algorithms for Science and Technology*, exposes students to HPC tools, algorithms, and technologies through practical applications. The third part, *Practical HPC Project*, involves hands-on participation in an active research project.

The HPCT course is offered during the second part of the MHPC program as a two-week intensive, hands-on course in configuring and managing HPC systems. It introduces students to fundamental topics including network administration, node provisioning, configuration management, software environments, and job scheduling. A key feature of the course is its hands-on approach, enabling students to set up their own clusters from scratch and manage systems both with and without physical access.

The HPCT course was first offered in person during the spring of 2019. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was transitioned to an online format from 2020 to 2022. This shift introduced several challenges, particularly in maintaining a hands-on experience without physical hardware access. To address these issues, the course was redesigned using a flipped-classroom model [4], in which participants review instructional materials—including lecture videos and supporting documents—prior to attending synchronous sessions. These sessions are instructor-led and focus on troubleshooting, discussion, and hands-on support using dedicated training resources provided by Temple University. This pedagogical model helped maintain engagement and flexibility during the online offerings while preserving the emphasis on hands-on experience during live sessions, rather than spending this valuable time on lectures.

Although the course returned to in-person instruction in 2022, the materials developed for the online version remain

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in active use and continue to support classroom delivery. These materials are publicly available at <https://www.hpc.temple.edu/mhpc/hpc-technology/index.html> and serve as a semi-standalone resource. While some instructions reference MHPC-specific computational infrastructure, see Section IV, the majority of the content can be readily adapted to other environments. Making the course materials openly accessible has significantly broadened their reach, enabling learners, educators, and HPC practitioners outside the MHPC program to explore and benefit from the course independently.

This paper provides an overview of the HPCT course, including its curriculum, methodology, and supporting infrastructure; it also summarizes student feedback and concludes with planned improvements and future directions. By documenting the development and adaptation of this course, the aim is to support workforce development in the field of HPC and promote broader utilization of the resource.

II. COURSE CONTENTS

The HPCT course is a two-week intensive program designed to provide participants with a strong foundation in building, configuring, and operating high-performance computing clusters. The curriculum covers a wide range of topics, including:

- Network configuration
- Cluster environment setup
- Software module management
- Batch systems and job scheduling
- Cluster monitoring
- Configuration as code

These topics are structured into ten sequential exercises, each designed to build on the previous one. Below is a detailed breakdown of each exercise, including its learning objectives and practical outcomes.

Exercise 1: Configuring Hardware and Network

This exercise introduces students to the physical components of an HPC cluster. Participants assemble the hardware, configure BIOS settings, and establish basic network connectivity between nodes to prepare the system for further provisioning.

Exercise 2: Setting Up a Minimal Netboot Environment

Participants learn the fundamentals of network booting using the Preboot Execution Environment (PXE). They configure a minimal environment that enables compute nodes to boot over the network, laying the groundwork for automated system provisioning.

Exercise 3: Setting Up a Netboot Environment with Cobbler

Building on the previous exercise, students install and configure Cobbler [5] to automate operating system deployment across multiple nodes. This introduces them to scalable provisioning and centralized service management.

Exercise 4: Setting Up a Cluster Environment

In this exercise, students configure essential cluster services such as Domain Name Server (DNS), Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), and Network Time Protocol (NTP). These components ensure synchronized operations across nodes and form the backbone of a functional HPC environment.

Exercise 5: RPM Repositories with Cobbler

Students learn to manage software package distribution by creating and maintaining local RPM repositories. This allows consistent software installation across nodes and supports offline or controlled environments.

Exercise 6: Software Modules

This exercise introduces the Environment Modules system [6]. Students configure module files to enable users to easily load and switch between multiple versions of installed software packages on the cluster.

Exercise 7: Configuration with Ansible

Participants use Ansible [7] to automate system configuration. They develop playbooks and roles to apply consistent settings across master and compute nodes, reinforcing the concept of infrastructure as code.

Exercise 8: Creating a Batch System with Slurm

Students install and configure Slurm [8] as the job scheduler for the cluster. They define queues, submit test jobs, and implement basic job management scripts to support workload execution and resource sharing.

Exercise 9: OpenMPI and InfiniBand

This exercise focuses on installing and validating OpenMPI and InfiniBand. Participants test interconnect performance using MPI benchmarks and analyze communication behavior between nodes.

Exercise 10: Monitoring with Ganglia

In the final exercise, students deploy Ganglia [9] to monitor and visualize key system metrics such as CPU usage, memory, and network traffic. This enables them to assess cluster health and performance in real time.

Participants are expected to have prior experience with UNIX-based operating systems and collaborative development tools such as Git. For MHPC students, this preparation is covered in the first part of the program.

III. COURSE METHODOLOGY

The HPCT course can be delivered in both in-person and online formats. While the in-person format is preferred due to the structure of the MHPC program, the online version, developed during the COVID-19 pandemic, has made the course materials publicly available and accessible to a global audience. This section focuses on the methodology used

for the online format, which continues to inform classroom instruction even in the current in-person delivery model.

The transition to an online format in 2020 required a redesign of the course to preserve its hands-on nature. To meet this challenge, the course adopted a flipped-classroom model [4]. In this model, participants are expected to review course materials—such as lecture videos, step-by-step instructions, and supplementary readings, prior to attending live sessions. This model allows students to learn at their own pace and arrive prepared for synchronous sessions, which focus on troubleshooting, configuration walkthroughs, and reinforcement of key concepts through direct interaction with instructors.

All course materials are hosted on a dedicated website [10], which serves as a central hub for students. The materials include lecture recordings, written instructions, annotated command references, and practical exercises. These resources are available at any time and from any location, providing flexibility and continuity of learning. Each exercise is available as a separate web page with detailed instructions, commands, and configuration examples, enabling participants to follow the material independently at their own pace.

Synchronous sessions are conducted via Zoom, where instructors provide live demonstrations, address student questions, and troubleshoot configuration issues. These sessions emphasize collaborative learning and encourage engagement through real-time discussion and problem solving.

To support the hands-on component, a dedicated training cluster is made available remotely for the duration of the course. However, access is typically extended by an additional month to allow students to complete exercises and refine their reports. Further details on this infrastructure are provided in Section IV. This infrastructure was critical to preserving the hands-on nature of the course during the online format, allowing students to fully engage with system-level configuration tasks remotely. Each participant or pair of participants is assigned a “subcluster” for experimentation and testing.

The course also incorporates a collaborative learning model [11]. Students are paired and encouraged to work together on exercises, fostering peer-to-peer learning. This collaboration enables students to support one another and share problem-solving strategies in real time.

Assessment is based on multiple factors. Each day, participants submit a brief progress report in their fork of the course’s GitHub repository. These reports summarize what was completed, issues encountered, and how they were resolved. Reports are expected to be written in the participant’s own words and include summaries, notes, and relevant configuration files. Additionally, short quizzes are administered throughout the course to reinforce core concepts and provide checkpoints for understanding.

The grading breakdown is as follows: 40% based on submitted reports, 30% on the successful completion of exercises, and 30% on quiz performance.

Fig. 1. Summary of the training cluster setup used for the HPCT course. Each “subcluster” consists of one master node and three compute nodes. All master nodes are reachable from a bastion host. The training cluster supports up to ten “subclusters.”

IV. COURSE INFRASTRUCTURE

To support the hands-on experience, the course relies on a dedicated training cluster and a small laboratory environment.

The training cluster is hosted at Temple University and is remotely accessible. It consists of 50 compute nodes connected via an InfiniBand fabric. These nodes are organized into ten “subclusters,” each composed of one master node and three compute nodes. This layout allows the course to accommodate up to ten participant groups simultaneously. The remaining ten nodes serve as spares to replace failed hardware or enable temporary expansion as needed. Each master node is accessible through a shared bastion host, which manages access and security. Figure 1 shows a representation of three subclusters within this setup.

In addition to the remote cluster, a laboratory at ICTP is available for local instruction. The lab contains eight physical workstations, each with a master node and two dedicated compute nodes; see Figure 2 for a graphical representation. This environment supports the same software stack and course content as the remote system and is used when teaching the course on-site in Trieste.

The equipment used in both the remote training cluster and the MHPC laboratory was sourced from decommissioned hardware, meaning there are no special requirements to adopt this course in other contexts. The only necessary features are those commonly available in standard rack servers, such as a BMC interface, at least two Ethernet ports, and approximately 20 GB of local disk space.

V. COURSE PERCEPTION

The success of the High-Performance Computing Technologies course can be measured not only by the number of students who completed it but also by the feedback received from participants. At the end of each offering, MHPC students submit anonymous evaluations to the program coordinator.

Fig. 2. Hardware configuration of each “cluster” station in the MHPC laboratory. The master node is connected to the compute nodes through two separate networks: one for managing the Board Management Controller (BMC) via the management network, and the other for internal cluster communication over SSH.

Overall, the feedback has been overwhelmingly positive. Students consistently report that they find the course useful, well-structured, and directly relevant to their development as HPC professionals.

The flipped-classroom model has been particularly well received. Students appreciated the ability to review materials at their own pace before attending live sessions. This structure helped them enter the synchronous sessions with a better understanding of the material and allowed instructors to focus on troubleshooting and deeper discussion.

The organization of the course was another area frequently praised. Students noted the clarity of the written instructions, the structured layout of the website, and the use of GitHub repositories for tracking and submitting work. In terms of support, students found the instructors to be responsive and helpful.

Constructive feedback has also helped shape improvements to the course. Some students suggested that the two-week time frame was too short to complete all exercises, especially for those new to system-level configuration. Others proposed introducing automated testing to verify exercise results instead of requiring daily written reports. While reports remain a core part of the assessment process, these suggestions have informed discussions about improving the course’s flexibility and assessment methods.

Across all editions, students have described the course as challenging but rewarding. Many commented that it was one of the few opportunities in the MHPC program to work closely with bare-metal systems in a controlled, production-like environment.

VI. FUTURE WORK

As the field of high-performance computing continues to evolve, the HPCT course must remain aligned with current software, hardware, and user needs. One ongoing effort involves updating the course content and training infrastructure to support more recent versions of Red Hat-based operating systems.

In response to increased demand for training in emerging computational domains, future iterations of the course aim to expand the scope of content. Planned additions include modules focused on installing and managing software stacks using Spack [12].

Improving the delivery and accessibility of the course remains a priority. While the in-person format has resumed, the online materials continue to be used and expanded. Future efforts will focus on enhancing interactivity through instructional videos, guided simulations, and virtual labs. These additions will support hybrid and asynchronous learning models and further broaden access to the course.

In terms of infrastructure, there is an initiative to explore the use of virtualization to emulate “subclusters,” enabling the course to function as a fully stand-alone offering without the need for dedicated physical hardware.

Student feedback will continue to guide future improvements. Suggestions such as integrating automated validation of configurations and expanding support materials are under active consideration. These enhancements aim to improve the student experience and help instructors more effectively assess progress, while maintaining the hands-on spirit of the course.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND COURSE AVAILABILITY

The High-Performance Computing Technologies (HPCT) course provides a comprehensive and practical learning experience for students seeking hands-on training in configuring and managing HPC clusters. With a strong emphasis on real-world tools and system-level configuration, the course prepares participants to work with the types of environments commonly found in research computing facilities.

Delivered within the MHPC program, the course adopts a flipped-classroom model and emphasizes active learning. Students are expected to review lecture videos and documentation in advance, and then apply that knowledge during instructor-led sessions and guided exercises. The supporting training infrastructure enables participants to install, configure, and operate their own isolated HPC environments.

To facilitate this experience, the course leverages a dedicated training cluster with up to ten bare-metal subclusters, along with an on-site laboratory equipped with physical workstations. This infrastructure supports both online and in-person instruction and ensures that each student can complete a realistic set of system administration tasks.

Since its first offering in 2019, the course has been taught six times and has reached approximately 80 students. Feedback has been consistently positive. However, some students have noted that the two-week period can be short, particularly for those with less experience in system-level work. To help address this, access to the training cluster is usually extended for one month after the instructional period, allowing students to complete exercises and refine their reports.

All course materials are publicly available at <https://www.hpc.temple.edu/mhpc/hpc-technology/index.html>. While many examples and instructions reference the MHPC infrastructure, the underlying methods and exercises are broadly applicable to

other systems. With its open materials and practical focus, the course serves as a valuable resource for students, instructors, and institutions interested in teaching HPC system administration skills.

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